

MODERN SOLUTIONS TO THE ORIGIN OF ARRHYTHMIA AS A SYMPTOM OF VARIOUS DISEASES

Rashidova Maftuna

Axmedov Abbos

Boltayev Xusan

Osmanov Tamal

Samarkand State Medical University, Department of Therapy, Cardiology and Functional
Diagnostics, 1st year ordinators

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Abstract. *Arrhythmia is a pathological condition in which heart rate, rhythm and sequence of heart contractions are disturbed. This is the general name of pathology, which is characterized by any deviation from the normal state of the heart. There are several types of arrhythmia, each of which has its own symptoms and causes. Let's take a closer look at what arrhythmia is, how it manifests itself, how many types there are, and how to treat them.*

Arrhythmia attacks can occur in both young and old age. Of course, adults are more prone to heart problems, but even children suffer from arrhythmias. Pathology can be congenital or acquired. The second type is more common.

Normal heart rate is 60-80 beats per minute. With changed indicators, arrhythmia develops, which can lead to harmful consequences.

Key words: *arrhythmia, types, prevention, symptoms.*

The urgency of the problem; The information in this section cannot be used for self-diagnosis and self-treatment. In case of pain or other exacerbation of the disease, diagnostic tests should be prescribed only by the attending physician. You should contact your doctor for a diagnosis and to prescribe the right treatment. In order to accurately evaluate the results of your analyzes over time, it is preferable to conduct research in the same laboratory, since different laboratories may use different research methods and units of measurement to perform the same analysis.

Research materials and methods: There are several types of arrhythmia. Specialists have studied them in detail and individual treatment is selected for each type. Division occurs depending on which part of the heart causes problems. There are 3 main types in total: sinus, ventricular, atrial. They also differ in heart rate. The main types of arrhythmia:

Observed results: Tachycardia. A condition where the pulse rate exceeds 80 beats. Seizures occur during heavy physical exertion, which is considered normal. But if the body is calm and the heart rate is high, this may indicate pathology.

Bradycardia. A type of arrhythmia in which the heart beats less than 60 times per minute. It can appear when the patient feels well, but if the patient regularly feels bad, this indicates the development of pathological processes.

Paroxysmal disorders. This is a condition in which the pulse of a completely healthy person increases dramatically, the heart begins to beat so hard that it is impossible to count the beats. As a rule, their frequency reaches 200 beats per minute. This is a type of tachycardia that causes severe weakness, general disorder and even loss of consciousness. In this case, immediate medical attention is required, this is a very dangerous situation that can cause irreversible processes.

Extrasystole. It appears for no reason. Premature contractions are associated with a normal heart rhythm. This attack is caused by vegetative-vascular dystonia, a high level of stress.

Atrial fibrillation of the heart. The most common type. An important phase of the heart rhythm - due to the loss of atrial contraction, the muscle fibers stop working in sync. That's why they flicker or "blink". The ventricles also begin to work in sync. It is one of the most common heart diseases and occurs in men and women of almost any age.

If symptoms indicating the disease appear, you should immediately contact specialists for help and start a course of recovery. Treatment of cardiac arrhythmia is simple if it is started on time and all the requirements of specialists are followed. Otherwise, if the disease is not taken into account, serious pathologies will develop, which will even lead to death.

Summary: With cardiac arrhythmia, the state of health deteriorates significantly. Shortness of breath, headache and other symptoms of arrhythmia appear. But they can pass quickly enough, and the patient immediately forgets about the deterioration of his health. However, this syndrome indicates the presence of a malfunction in the body, if you do not respond in time, the cardiovascular system can suffer great damage; Let's look at the consequences of frequent attacks:

anxiety and stress develop;

the disease contributes to the formation of unconsciousness, there is a risk of falling;

the body suffers from blood starvation, all organs suffer from heart disease;

dangerous heart diseases develop, for example, coronary heart disease, etc.;

there is a risk of stroke;

sudden cardiac arrest and death are possible.

Regular pain and discomfort in the heart area may indicate the presence of the disease. Arrhythmia symptoms are very obvious, but people rarely worry about their health after it passes. You should not treat yourself like this, if you suspect problems, you should contact a specialist and undergo an examination. With the help of diagnostics, you can easily identify heart diseases and prescribe effective treatment. Take care of the main mechanism, if you provide help in time, the disease will be cured quickly.

The regular occurrence of arrhythmia affects the heart. Timely detection of heart pathology; There are a large number of treatment methods, which are selected depending on the type of heart arrhythmia. But first the diagnosis is made. If you feel that your health is deteriorating and your heart needs help, contact a specialist. Due to the obvious symptoms of arrhythmia, you can notice the pathology yourself:

- sudden weakness appears;
- the heart begins to beat much faster;
- chest pain, feeling that there is pressure in this area;
- attack of suffocation;
- sudden onset of dizziness;
- may regularly lose consciousness;
- headache occurs.

Often, patients do not suspect the development of the disease. Arrhythmia symptoms are similar to other pathologies or simply factors that provoke such conditions. For example, headaches are often associated with stress. Chest pain syndrome is associated with physical activity. And the state of sudden loss of consciousness may be associated with feelings of hunger or mental fatigue. However, if there are signs of any of the attacks described above, you should immediately contact a specialist. In case of arrhythmia, we will tell you which doctor you should contact below.

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